

Contribution of fishery aquaculture to global carbon emission reduction

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1. Introduction

Carbon footprint is the total amount of greenhouse gas emissions produced by a person, event, institution, service, place, or product [1]. Carbon emissions caused by current human activities have created many problems, such as ocean acidification [2] and global warming [1]. Carbon emissions caused by human activities mainly come from the burning of fossil fuels. Taking aquaculture as an example, the industry has a history of thousands of years in Asia (especially China). Not only has the development of fisheries in Asia and the world been very mature, but therefore, the aquaculture industry, breeding facilities, aquatic fishing, etc. are the main sources of carbon emissions. The direct carbon emissions of marine fisheries mainly come from the diesel consumption of fishing boats during the fishing process, while the indirect carbon emissions of marine fisheries mainly come from the electricity consumption during the production process. Some Icelandic scientists have also proposed that the overall catch and abundance are the most important factors in determining carbon emissions. The greater the catch and the greater the abundance, the smaller the carbon emissions per unit output [3]. So how can we provide a sustainable supply of aquatic products to maintain the development of fisheries and agriculture-related industries while reducing the impact of fisheries on carbon emissions?

2. About ocean acidification

Ocean acidification refers to the phenomenon that the pH value of seawater in the earth's oceans decreases over time. Carbon dioxide emissions produced by human activities are the main cause of ocean acidification. This carbon dioxide will be absorbed by the ocean, producing carbonic acid that affects the pH value of seawater and seriously affects the survival of aquatic animals and plants. In the recorded years from 1991 to 2018, the ocean's level of acidification never stops. At present, the pH value of the global sea surface has dropped by about 0.1 compared with pre-industrialization, which means that the acidity of seawater has increased by

about 26% [4] (Fig. 1). Human progress never stops, and neither does environmental damage. First of all, one of the factors that greatly affects the carbon emissions of fishing activities is transportation. Generally, the traditional method is to go fishing by boat. Many fishing boats frequently go back and forth to the sea, which consumes a lot of fuel and causes very high carbon dioxide emissions. Is there any way to replace it?

3. First solution: the integrated farming platform

About this question, our idea is to use integrated farming platforms to replace the traditional method of conducting fishing by boat. Integrated farming platforms carry out farming in the sea, reducing land reclamation [the use of fuel in the process of reclaiming land] and land occupation. The vertical space breeding model can be used to superimpose breeding layers to increase the breeding density and achieve higher breeding output [5]. It can also be equipped with some wave energy and solar power generation equipment and energy storage devices to achieve complete self-sufficiency. Using these renewable energy sources instead of fossil fuels can effectively compensate for the high carbon dioxide emissions associated with fishery transport. In terms of the feasibility of the plan, China has already had examples. For instance, Penghu is one of the first integrated semi-submersible wave energy farming platforms in China. It is equipped with the wave energy and solar power generation equipment and energy storage devices mentioned above. It utilizes green energy by using sunlight and wave energy for energy conversion [6] and thereby reduces energy consumption. This method can culture a large amount of fish at a fixed location and time and reduce the frequency of fishing. Therefore, it reduces the use of fossil fuels and reduces carbon emissions. We believe this is a more efficient way of fishing.

Figure 1. Climatological distribution of global surface ocean pH on the total hydrogen scale [pHT] at in-situ temperature [7]

4. Carbon fixation in ocean

The existence of all life on earth is based on a natural mechanism in nature called carbon fixation. Taking the ecology in the ocean as an example, autotrophic microorganisms in the sea, such as algae, can perform photosynthesis and store carbon dioxide in the air in chemical forms such as carbohydrates in their bodies. Then fish prey on these autotrophic organisms and store them in their bodies. Carbon is fixed in their own bodies. These fish and feeder organisms are deposited to the seafloor when they die, so the carbon in the organisms successfully returns from the air to the soil to complete carbon fixation (Fig. 2). It is estimated that the ocean has absorbed approximately 40% of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions since the Industrial Revolution [Aronsohn, 2020] [3]. Carbon sequestration easily stores carbon dioxide from the air in the soil in the form of other carbon compounds and eventually returns to the ecosystem. Biological carbon sequestration is to use the photosynthesis of plants to improve the carbon absorption and storage capacity of the ecosystem, thereby reducing the concentration of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere and slowing down the trend of global warming. The methods used in traditional fisheries do not consider the number of fish species in the sea and are unsustainable. Therefore, the use of integrated breeding platforms cannot affect the

ecological environment and specific number characteristics of species in the ocean. We can thereby maintain a certain number of fish schools in the ocean and can also avoid fishing methods like trawling from destroying the habitat in the ocean. Prevent marine life from losing its habitat and causing a decline in population, maintain biodiversity in the ocean, and avoid the carbon sequestration process in which there are not enough fish in the ocean to eat autotrophs and die naturally.

5. Second solution: reusing of food waste

As we might know, our food contains carbon, but we often waste food in our daily lives, turning this wasted food into kitchen waste. As a result, carbon within this wasted food may not be able to return to the natural carbon cycle. The amount of food waste produced by each person and family every day is remarkable. In 2011, about 3600 tonnes of food waste were dumped in Hong Kong's landfills every day [9]. This is the equivalent weight of 300 double-decker buses and accounts for 40% of Hong Kong's municipal solid waste. The carbon in the kitchen waste cannot be returned to the natural ecosystem. We can use the food demand of aquaculture fisheries to regenerate these food wastes into fish food so that the accumulated carbon can be returned to the ecosystem and food chain again. This technology in re-

Figure 2. Overview of ocean carbon cycle and diatom carbon dioxide concentration mechanisms [8]

ality has been realized for a long time. A company from Hong Kong has studied the possibility of food chain recycling and developed a food waste conversion device [10]. It collects commercial food waste from nearby food factories and uses the machine to perform four processes: mincing, mixing, puffing, and drying. Food waste such as fruit peels, vegetables, and fish bones is converted into fish food for local fisheries. This food waste conversion device is assembled in a 20-foot container. The current prototype is located in Sheung Shui Kwu Tung. There are four main machines in the container house. Through a computer system and a

series of processing steps, the food waste conversion device converts fruit peels, vegetables, fish kitchen waste such as bones, and bean dregs into fish food (Fig. 3). After the team collected the food waste, they put it into a grinder to mince it into crumbs, mixed it, and added necessary corn flour and larvae as a nutritional source of feed. Finally, through the puffing and drying steps, the mixture is extruded into granular feed, and the granules are dehydrated and made into floatable water feed.

Figure 3. The procedure to converting food waste into fish food, from HK government

6. Summary

With advancements in technologies, we can eat fish at every meal. This is driven by the demand from humans' love of seafood and the prosperity of fishery development. But we do not know how to give back to nature. We believe that because of the advancement of science and technology, we can improve the shortcomings of traditional fisheries that damage the environment and adopt new breeding methods, such as the integrated breeding platform aforementioned, which is more efficient and environmentally friendly than methods such as fish ponds, and can further reduce carbon emissions and promote the development of green fisheries.

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